

Organizational Support and Emotional Labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital

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Abstract:

COVID-19 presented an unprecedented challenge for healthcare workers and systems around the world. This study explored the extent of organizational support and level of emotional labor of the employees in a government hospital in Negros Occidental amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. This is a mixed method research which also described the experiences of healthcare workers of a government hospital. A survey questionnaire thru google form was sent to 313 respondents and an online and face to face interview were done with 3 participants for the qualitative part. Age, sex, length of service, status of employment and division assigned were the demographic variables in the study. Based on the aspects of organizational support that includes; perceived organizational support, organizational empowerment and organizational rewards, employees rated these aspects as to great or to great extent of organizational support. On the part of Level of Emotional Labor, the overall result obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor. And it is also noted that on the aspect of deep acting, result showed that there is a high level of emotional labor for the employees of a government hospital. In conclusion, the findings provide a clear insight that employees of a government hospital are satisfied with extent of organizational support that the organization is providing them and maintains a moderately high level of emotional labor in the organization. For the qualitative side of study, the following themes resulted in the study: (4) significant themes described their experiences, namely: 1) Challenges experienced by healthcare workers, with sub themes (Workplace changes during the pandemic, work challenges brought by pandemic, Social stigma and discrimination, Mental and Emotional Health Concerns 2) Pulling through COVID-19 and 3) Support for Frontline Health Care Workers and 4) Healthcare workers' resilience.

Keywords: Business Administration, Organizational support, emotional labor, healthcare workers, concurrent mixed methods research design, Philippines

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

COVID-19 presented an unprecedented challenge for healthcare workers and systems worldwide (Leow et al., 2020). Healthcare professionals (HCPs) on the front lines against COVID-19 may face increased workload and stress (Islahuddin, 2020). They might go through traumatic experiences, need to learn how to deal with complexity, adapt to the new reality of work, and need emotional and interpersonal support (Dirani et al., 2020). Health care professionals want unambiguous assurance that their organization will support them and their families (Shanafelt et al., 2020). To help alleviate the anxiety of the healthcare workers, healthcare organizations ought to provide specific support to address their workers' concerns during the pandemic (Zhang et al., 2020). The management is encouraging their employees to give enough freedom in their work and apply their full potential and ability to carry out the organization's overall aims (Busara, 2020).

The challenges faced by healthcare workers in the current pandemic are substantially greater than those encountered in their normal work, and, understandably, the language of heroism has been evoked to praise them for their actions (Cox, 2020). The healthcare staff is one of the integral parts of the fight against this virus. As an instrument of the public health system, the healthcare staff protects the general population's health and wellness. They are the frontliners risking their safety and health and are responsible for activities related to COVID-19 (Hashim et al., 2021). Healthcare workers face pressure from the risk of infection, isolation, burnout, and public

discrimination, which adversely impact their overall well-being and their decision-making ability (Lijun Kang, Yi Li et al., 2020).

In the COVID-19 context, all health facilities should be equipped with the basic equipment to handle at least mild COVID-19 cases. All healthcare workers in either undesignated or designated health centers for COVID-19 treatment should be trained in handling COVID-19 cases (Onigbinde et al., 2020). Other proposed reciprocal duties that healthcare institutions have to their employees include clear communication regarding expectations and risks involved; adequate support, training, and resources to perform their duties; counseling and psychological support; support and compensation for their families if they die; and access to treatment or vaccination if it becomes available (Cox, 2020). Resilience to the situation arising from the pandemic was equally effective. Most societies and governments have attempted to boost resilience by labeling the HCWs as “heroes” and “warriors.” (Samavedam, 2022).

The main purpose of this study was to determine the extent of organizational support of the employees of a government hospital during this time of COVID-19 pandemic and their level of emotional labor and to describe the employees' experiences. The researcher finds this beneficial to study these specific aspects of the organization because the management can create/enhance policies for the well-being of the employees. Specifically, the result of this study will be the basis for human resource development plans that are also in line with the Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management (PRIME-HRM) Accreditation. PRIME-HRM stands for Program to Institutionalize Meritocracy and Excellence in Human Resource Management. It is a mechanism to support the attainment of the Civil Service Commission's vision of becoming a Center of Excellence for Human Resource and Organization Development (CSC Memorandum Circular No. 3, s. 2012).

Current State of Knowledge

Nursing, by its nature, is an occupation full of emotions. Every nurse undergoes both good and bad days in a workplace as in any other profession. However, nursing might be emotionally more demanding than many other jobs in the service industry, since most nursing environments are associated with taking care of physically and/or mentally fragile patients (Lee & Jang, 2020). Care is the core of nursing practice. Nurses must forge a caring relationship as opposed to a simple task-oriented one with patients in pain, which can render them emotionally exhausted and may produce conflict. Despite this, nurses must demonstrate appropriate emotional management when providing services to patients face-to-face. In other words, nurses must engage in emotional labor (Back et al., 2020) and always take into consideration customer's satisfaction. As discussed by Haozhen, L., Vito Jr., M. M., & Bautista, M. A. (2024) in their study that customer support responsiveness and effectiveness are pivotal in addressing user inquiries, technical issues, and overall customer satisfaction.

Contract staff may lose more passion for their work than permanent staffs do when experiencing occupational burnout, leading to increased documented instances of poor quality of care provided by contract staff (Chao et al., 2016). Moreover, such employees were least motivated to perform enthusiastic work, especially when they perceive that their contract will to be terminated after specific time (Sarmad et al., 2021). Organizations need to focus on organizational practices as employees' perception of organizational support is related to the way they express their emotions during customer interactions. A strong sense of organizational support will also promote a stronger professional identity; further, a strong professional identity completely mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on emotional labor (Zeng et al., 2021).

The COVID-19 pandemic was a global shock that disrupted the way people work. As most countries attempted to slow down the rapid spread of the virus by introducing social distancing measures, organizations were forced to swiftly implement new ways of working such as remote working or to organize different types of workflow and interactions between work colleagues or between employees and customers in physical locations (Mihalache & Mihalache, 2022). Workplace management during and after the COVID-19 pandemic has become a global challenge. Organizations have been committed to modifying their office workplace in various ways to comply with the COVID-19 measures and suit the working practice in the new normal (Hou et al., 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic has created challenges for services provided face-to-face. The high risk of contagion and the need for physical distancing have impelled a reorganization of the way services are delivered at the street level and how frontline workers (FLW) interact with citizens (Lotta et al., 2021). Healthcare providers are the frontline soldiers battling against the coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic (Koontalay et al., 2021).

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on organizational support theory by (Eisenberger et al., 1986) and The Affective Events Theory (AET) of Weiss and Cropanzano (1996). Organizational support theory (OST) is considered an important theoretical foundation for the perception of organizational support entrenched with social exchange theory (Imran et al., 2020). While the Affective Events Theory (AET) of Weiss and Cropanzano (1996) strongly emphasizes the importance of emotion, it shows how important the emotion of the members is in organizational management (Choi & Kim, 2015).

Organizational Support Theory (OST) is considered an important theoretical foundation for the perception of organizational support entrenched with social exchange theory (Imran et al., 2020). According to organizational support theory, employees value POS partly because it meets their needs for approval, esteem, and affiliation and provides comfort during times of stress (Eisenberger et al., 2016). OST maintains that, based on the norm of reciprocity, workers trade effort and dedication to their organization for such tangible incentives as pay and fringe benefits and such socio-emotional benefits as esteem, approval, and caring (Baran et al., 2016).

In other words, an employee's perception of organizational commitment to him or contributes to the level of commitment to the organization (Masumu et al., 2006). Organizational support theory emphasizes that organizations should identify the needs of their employees and do their best to meet the needs of their employees so that they are aware of employers' support (Liu, 2018). Organizational Support Theory explains that it is the general point of employees that they feel more empowered at their workplace when they have organizational support (Saeed, 2015).

Affective Events Theory is a model describing within-person changes in affective states, their root in events of both a stochastic and regular nature and their influences on concurrent changes in performance-related behaviors (Cropanzano et al., 2017). AET emphasizes events in the workplace as important sources for triggering employee emotions which are then closely linked to work behavior (Boulter & Boddy, 2021). AET holds that organizational events trigger affective responses in organizational members, with consequences for workplace attitudes, cognition, and behavior (Ashton-James & Ashkanasy, 2008). More specifically, AET suggests that, on the one hand, affective states like moods and emotions typically comprise physiological components that can have many effects at the time they occur (Wegge et al., 2006).

Emotional labor is the process of employees managing their emotions to conform to organizational expectations during customer interactions (Gabriel & Diefendorff, 2015). The most common strategies individuals employ to adhere to the organizationally - desired display rules are deep acting and surface acting (Barry et al., 2019). Engaging in surface acting daily may result in problems that are likely to exhaust employees' resources in the short run and, consequently, hinder the recovery process. In contrast, engaging in deep acting may allow reserving and even gaining resources at work that may facilitate recovery after work (Xanthopoulou et al., 2018).

Objectives

The study's main purpose was to determine the Extent of Organizational Support and Level of Emotional Labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the extent of the organizational support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, when taken as a whole and grouped according to age, sex, length of service, status of employment, and division assigned; 2) the Level of Emotional Labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of the COVID-19 pandemic, when taken as a whole and grouped according to age, sex, length of service, the status of employment, and division assigned; 3) the significant difference in the organizational support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex, length of service, and division assigned; 4) the significant difference in the Level of Emotional Labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic when taken as a whole and grouped according to sex, length of service, and division assigned; and 5) significant relationship between organizational support and emotional labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental at the time of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Research Methodology

This section discusses the type of research used in the investigation, the research design, setting, the study subjects and population, the research instrument, its validity and reliability, the data gathering procedure and the statistical tools that were used for analyzing the data gathered for the study.

Research Design

The study mainly used the concurrent triangulation mixed methods research design. Mixed methods research is an approach that combines both quantitative and qualitative methods into a single study in order to provide a broader and more complete vision of a problem (Ririn, 2020). In the concurrent design, qualitative and quantitative data are collected in a single phase because the general aim of this approach is to understand better or obtain a more developed understanding of the phenomenon under study (Warfa, 2016).

Respondents

The respondents of this study were the job order and plantilla employees of the hospital coming from the different divisions of the organization. The hospital had a total population of 1668 employees (HOPSSD/Finance Offices under MCC – 327 employees, Nursing Division – 413 employees, Medical Division – 928 employees). Using Cochran’s Formula, with a 5% margin of error and 95% confidence level, there were 313 respondents for the study. The Cochran formula was used to calculate the essential sample size for the required precision, confidence level, and the estimated proportion of the attribute present in the population (Nanjundeswaraswamy & Divakar, 2021). The researcher used stratified random sampling proportionate allocation to pick out the respondents. In this study, the respondents were divided based on their division assigned1. HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC 2. Medical Division 3. Nursing Division. Using stratified random sampling proportionate allocation formula, 63 respondents came from HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC, 78 from Nursing Division, and 172 from the Medical Division.

Instruments

The instrument that was used was an adapted-modified survey questionnaire. The questionnaire on “Measuring Emotional Labor Among young workers” (Castro et al., 2006) was used to gather appropriate data on the level of the emotional labor of the employees. Furthermore, the extent of organizational support for the hospital employees was collected using the questionnaire from “Perceived Organizational Support.” The questionnaire was answered using a Likert scale. The technique used to establish the validity of the questionnaires was the content validity ratio (CVR) by Lawshe, in which jury validators were asked to check whether items in the questionnaire were Essential, Useful but not essential, or Not Essential. Content validity is the degree to which a tool captures components of the construct it intends to measure. Lawshe’s content validity ratio is a rigorous methodological approach to assessing the validity of individual items and the overall questionnaire (Kennedy et al., 2019). The researcher went through the validity testing of the instrument with seventeen (17) experts at the doctorate level. With the panel size of 17, required content validity ratio is .529, the content validity index of the instrument resulted in 0.751, which means the instrument passed the validity test. And for reliability, a pilot test was conducted at another government hospital in Negros Occidental to ensure the instrument's good reliability. A dry run of the survey questionnaire was conducted on the 30 employees of the hospital. The reliability testing of the instrument resulted in .095 for organizational support and emotional labor and an overall result of 0.95 reliability coefficient value.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher steered the following procedures to acquire significant data related to his study: After securing approval from the Hospital Research Committee and Research Ethics and Review Committee, and after the research instrument's validity and reliability, the online survey link was sent to the respondents for them to answer. The researcher strictly checked and accounted daily for the online survey to closely monitor the result, as google forms updated the results in real-time. For the qualitative process, a non-directive interview of the participants was conducted. The researcher did a face-to-face and online, one-on-one interview in compliance with safety protocol. Before the interview started, the researcher asked for participants' consent, recording everything being asked and answered. Upon the go signal of the participant, the researcher recorded the interview using a smartphone. Two phones were used to ensure all data were gathered accordingly and reliably. A Series of interviews were conducted until data saturation to replicate the study. Tokens like ball pens, tumblers, or other things needed while on a tour of duty, were given to the participants.

Statistical Treatment

After the responses to the items in the online survey questionnaire were collated, tallied, and tabulated to determine the profile of the employees' frequency, scoring was used.

The mean and standard deviation were used for Problems 1 and 2 as to the Extent of Organizational Support and Level of Emotional Labor of the Employees. The mean score range in the questionnaire was likewise determined and interpreted.

Mean Range	Organizational Support Level	Emotional Labor Extent	
5.18	6.00	Very High	Very Great
4.34	5.17	High	Great
3.51	4.33	Moderately High	Moderately Great

2.68	3.50	Moderately Low	Moderately Low
1.84	2.67	Low	Low
1.00	1.83	Very Low	Very Low

For Problems 3 & 4 on determining the significant difference in the Level of Emotional Labor and Extent of Organizational Support of the Employees when grouped according to age, sex, length of service, the status of employment, Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal Wallis were used based on the distribution and characteristics of the data set. The researcher used a spreadsheet's data analytics function to analyze the data.

For Problems No. 5 on determining the significant relationship between Emotional Labor and Organizational Support, Spearman's rho was used based on the distribution and characteristics of the data set correlation. This is the most widely used correlation statistic to measure the degree of the relationship between linearly related variables.

Ethical Considerations

Through the survey and interview conducted with the respondents/participants, the researcher drew out the best recommendation and conclusion for the study that would be beneficial to the participants. The researcher ensured that the result of the study would be very valuable to both the organization and employees. The researcher asked for the division chiefs' approval to formally start the data gathering. The researcher explained to respondents /participants that they would voluntarily participate and have the right to withdraw from the interview. Since the researcher used an online platform, participants were informed that their responses would be treated with full confidentiality, and whatever they shared during the interview, only the researcher had access to it. Also, the researcher assures the respondents of their privacy and the confidentiality of the responses including the risk and benefits.

Results and Discussion:

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study and analyses of these data facilitated by the identified appropriate statistical tools. It interprets the results derived from the analyses.

Table 1]

Extent of the Organizational Support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the Time of COVID-19 Pandemic

Variables	Perceived Organizational Support			Organizational Empowerment			Rewards			Overall Organizational Support		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Sex												
Male (136)	4.62	0.766	Great	4.80	0.781	Great	4.69	0.863	Great	4.70	0.738	Great
Female (177)	4.57	0.915	Great	4.67	1.007	Great	4.57	1.064	Great	4.60	0.951	Great
Age												
18-25 years old (21)	4.48	1.001	Great	4.49	0.970	Great	4.55	0.930	Great	4.50	0.925	Great
26-41 years old (211)	4.56	0.849	Great	4.71	0.933	Great	4.55	1.020	Great	4.60	0.873	Great
42-65 years old (81)	4.71	0.821	Great	4.85	0.852	Great	4.83	0.873	Great	4.79	0.819	Great
Length of Service												
5 Years and Below (113)	4.59	0.898	Great	4.71	0.875	Great	4.63	0.981	Great	4.64	0.875	Great
6-10 Years (140)	4.57	0.789	Great	4.71	0.933	Great	4.60	0.985	Great	4.62	0.836	Great
11-15 Years (24)	4.47	1.180	Great	4.62	1.130	Great	4.38	1.175	Great	4.49	1.133	Great
16 Years and Above (36)	4.75	0.690	Great	4.92	0.833	Great	4.87	0.804	Great	4.84	0.731	Great
Status of Employment												
Plantilla (252)	4.54	0.880	Great	4.68	0.957	Great	4.62	0.993	Great	4.61	0.892	Great
Job Order (61)	4.79	0.702	Great	4.93	0.695	Great	4.64	0.941	Great	4.79	0.728	Great
Division Assigned												
HOPSSD/Finance/Office under MCC(63)	4.94	0.610	Great	5.02	0.661	Great	4.95	0.675	Great	4.96	0.591	Great
Medical/Allied Medical Division (172)	4.65	0.674	Great	4.85	0.673	Great	4.71	0.773	Great	4.73	0.657	Great
Nursing Division (78)	4.19	1.171	Moderately Great	4.22	1.296	Moderately Great	4.17	1.378	Moderately Great	4.19	1.217	Moderately Great
As a whole (313)	4.5	0.85	Great	4.7	0.91	Great	4.6	0.98	Great	4.6	0.86	Great
	9	3		3	6		2	2		4	5	

Note: MG = Moderately Great

Table 1 below presents the summary of results of the different variables. The results show the overall result for the sub aspects of organizational support as whole. For the perceived organizational support, the employees rated the extent of Perceived organizational support as great with a mean score of 4.59 with standard deviation of 0.853. For the organizational empowerment it was rated also as great with a mean score of 4.73 and standard deviation of 0.916, and for the organizational rewards, it obtained the rating of great having the mean score of 4.62 and a

standard deviation of 0.982. And the overall result for the extent of Organizational support is great obtained an overall mean score of 4.64 and overall standard deviation of 0.865.

Organizational Support in the demographic variable of **sex**. The overall result shows that both Male and Female employees of a government hospital rated the extent of Organizational Support as *great*, that male employees obtained a higher mean score of 4.70 compared to female employees that obtained a mean score of 4.60 with the standard deviation of 0.738 and .951 respectively.

Perceived organizational support as part of the aspects of Organizational Support rated as *great*, that male employee obtained a higher mean score of 4.62 compared to female employees that obtained a mean score of 4.57 with standard deviation of 0.766 and 0.915 respectively. According to one of the respondents, *"she believes that there is no difference as how a male or female perceived the extent of organizational support because it is the same way how they can feel about the support being provided or given by the management or the institution, thus, she thinks it will be also the same support that will be given to a female and male employee."*

The result implies that both male and female felt and received the same extent of organizational support. In this organization, there is an equal support given to both male and female employees. Looking at the result, both male and female employees rated the support of the organization great and it is being supported with the stakeholder's perspective. This only shows that there is no favorable support given for male or female employees, both felt the same level of support.

In the demographic variable of **age**, the overall result shows *great* extent of organizational support, employees in the age range of 42-65 y/o obtained the highest mean score of 4.79 and followed by the age group of 26-41 y/o with a mean score of 4.60 and age group 18-25 y/o obtained a mean score of 4.50 with the standard deviation of .0819, 0.873 and 0.925, respectively.

Perceived organizational support as part of the aspects of Organizational Support shows results that employees in the age range of 18-25 y/o, 26-41 y/o, 42-65 y/o of a government hospital rated the extent of perceived organizational support as *great* having the mean score of 4.48, 4.56 and 4.71 with standard deviation of 1.001, 0.849 and 0.821 respectively. From an informal interview, one staff said: *"Regardless of the age even if you are a newbie or retirable, the same support is given to you. That is why no matter what your age is, she thinks that if you feel that you are supported by the management you will still appreciate it"*. As to variable of age in this study, the same ratings were given by the employees considering the age. This simply implies that there is still an equal support to all in the organization whether you are new or about to retire. The same extent of support given to younger and older employees. The organization is giving the same level of support to those new to the organization or to those who will in the retiring stage.

In the demographic variable of **length of service**, the result shows that employees of a government hospital rated the extent of organizational support as *great*, the tenure of service of 16 years and above obtained the highest mean score of 4.84 followed by 6-10 years with a mean score of 4.62 then tenure of 5 years and below with a mean score of 4.64 and 11-15 years of service that obtained the mean score of 4.49 with the standard deviation of 0.731, 0.836, 0.875 and 1.333 respectively.

Perceived organizational support as part of the aspects of Organizational Support shows result that employees in the tenure of service of 5 years and below, 6-10 years, 11-15 years and 16 years and above of a government hospital rated the extent of perceived organizational support as *great* having the mean score of 4.59, 4.57, 4.47 and 4.75 with standard deviation of 0.898, 0.789, 1.180 and 0.690 respectively. One employee from HOPSSD said: *"For him, those who stayed long right now in the organization are more favored in terms of the support like encouragement and rewards, or let us say in terms of promotion. Tenured employees are more likely to be promoted first, well I must agree with their experience, but I hope competency will also be a big basis also."*

As to the tenure of service, the result implies that the extent of organizational support felt by those in the early years and already tenured in the organization are the same. However, in the stakeholder's perspective it is believed that those who served in the institution for a long time get more support especially in terms of promotion. For the aspect of rewards, experience is one of the factors for promotion, there is a specific points given to those who are in the service for the institution for quite some time. Tenured employees may have proven themselves to the organization and made remarkable and significant contribution in the achievement of organizational goals.

In the demographic variable of **status of employment**, the overall result shows that employees with the employment status of plantilla and job order of a government hospital rated the extent of organizational support as *great*, with job order personnel which obtained the higher result having the overall mean score of 4.79 and plantilla staff with 4.61 mean score with the standard deviation of 0.728 and 0.892, respectively.

Perceived organizational support as part of the aspects of Organizational Support shows results that employees with the employment status of plantilla and job order of a government hospital rated the extent of perceived organizational support as *great* having the mean score of 4.54 and 4.79 with standard deviation of 0.880 and 0.702, respectively. One Job Order Staff shared: *"The attention and support given to the staff whether job order or plantilla are the same. The management made sure that whatever benefits that the permanent or plantilla personnel are receiving, same will be provided to JO also. Like in terms of a specific philhealth share, it is also given to Job Order. As to the salary, salary of JO is patterned also to the lowest salary grade for plantilla personnel, that is higher than the minimum wage"*

Based on the result and as to the stakeholder's perspective, both plantilla and job order employees rated great the extent of organizational support. This implies that the management provides the same amount of support, monetary and non-monetary to the staff, regardless of the empment status. There is no favorable support given to those with permanent position or those plantilla personnel, the management of the institution made sure that whatever benefits or support that are given to plantilla personnel are also shared to Job Order staff. Plantilla personnel were not set apart from the JO staff in the involvement of some activities of the institution also.

Nevertheless, considering the type of employees such as contractual and permanent employees in distinctive sector, there are no conclusive evidences as to their perceived organizational support. Since there is no conclusive evidence from the existing literature about contractual and permanent employees' perspective, which makes it more intriguing to find the variable of interest. Statistical results confirmed that organizational empowerment has positive role in enhancing the professionalism among permanent employees in contrast to contractual employees (Faridi & Baloch, 2019). POS enhances both in-role performance of permanent and part-time employees such as goal attainment and extra role performance such as helping and supportive behavior toward coworkers (Maan et al., 2020).

In the demographic variable of **division assigned**, the overall result shows that employees of a government hospital in the HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC division and Medical/Allied Medical Division rated extent of organizational support as *great* having the overall mean score of 4.96 and 4.73 with the overall standard deviation result of 0.591 and 0.657 respectively, while in the Nursing Division, the employees rated *moderately great* having the overall mean score of 4.19 and overall standard deviation result of 1.217.

Perceived organizational support as part of the aspects of Organizational Support shows results that employees of a government hospital in the HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC division and Medical/Allied Medical Division rated the extent of perceived organizational support as *great* having the mean score of 4.94 and 4.65 with standard deviation of 0.610 and 0.674 respectively, while in the Nursing Division, the employees rated *moderately great* having the mean score of 4.19 with standard deviation of 1.171. One of the nurses shared: *"For us nurses, and other assigned in the nursing service division, I think most us rated only moderately high because of the delayed benefits given coming from the national government. Our work is a high risk, we make sacrifices, we keep ourselves away from our family just to serve COVID patients but during this trying time healthcare workers are not given much attention. We felt tired of wearing full PPEs. I hope the national government will take a look at this"*.

The result for HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC division and Medical/Allied Medical Division are great, however, to nursing division, they only rated moderately great. This implies the staff under the nursing division felt lesser support from the organization. This is for the reason that, during the pandemic, nursing staff deals more of COVID patients and needs more of emotional and mental support. The result and the perspective of a nurse is a clear manifestation of the extent of support they received or felt during the pandemic. Management support was being tested during the peak of the pandemic, from the benefits given to the staff, and as well is mental and emotional supports that are extended to the staff of the different division.

Table 2

Level of Emotional Labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the Time of COVID-19 Pandemic

Variables	Surface Acting			Deep Acting			Overall Emotional Labor		
	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int	M	SD	Int
Sex									
Male	3.86	0.991	MH	4.43	0.767	Hi	4.11	0.720	MH
Female	3.85	1.095	MH	4.54	0.697	Hi	4.15	0.767	MH
Age									
18-25 years old	4.23	0.669	MH	4.25	0.695	MH	4.24	0.491	MH
26-41 years old	3.89	1.043	MH	4.48	0.744	Hi	4.15	0.756	MH
42-65 years old	3.67	1.118	MH	4.58	0.690	Hi	4.07	0.777	MH
Length of Service									
5 Years and Below	3.83	1.022	MH	4.39	0.749	Hi	4.08	0.765	MH
6-10 Years	3.93	1.011	MH	4.50	0.738	Hi	4.18	0.714	MH
11-15 Years	3.62	1.371	MH	4.57	0.593	Hi	4.03	0.869	MH
16 Years and Above	3.78	1.052	MH	4.71	0.682	Hi	4.19	0.731	MH
Status of Employment									
Plantilla	3.82	1.041	MH	4.43	0.722	Hi	4.09	0.743	MH
Job Order	3.99	1.080	MH	4.73	0.717	Hi	4.31	0.738	MH
Division Assigned									
HOPSSD/Finance/Office under MCC	3.80	1.158	MH	4.52	0.630	Hi	4.12	0.821	MH
Medical/Allied Medical Division	3.75	1.037	MH	4.58	0.659	Hi	4.12	0.742	MH
Nursing Division	4.11	0.948	MH	4.26	0.893	MH	4.18	0.697	MH
As a whole	3.85	1.049	MH	4.49	0.729	Hi	4.13	0.746	MH

Note: MH = Moderately high; Hi = high

Table 2 presents the summary of results on the employees' emotional labor. The result shows the overall result for the sub aspects of emotional labor as a whole. For the surface acting, the employees obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor with a mean score of 3.85 with the standard deviation of 1.049. For the deep acting, the result was high level of emotional labor with a mean score of 4.49 and a standard deviation of 0.729. And the overall result for the level of Emotional Labor is moderately high and obtained an overall mean score of 4.13 with the standard deviation of 0.746. The results of the variables when grouped according to age, sex, length of service, status of employment and division assigned as to the different aspects of organizational support were discussed consequently.

In the demographic variable of sex, the result shows both Male and Female employees of a government hospital obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, with female employees obtained a higher mean score of 4.15 than male employees with a mean score of 4.11 with the standard deviation of 0.720 and 0.767 respectively.

Surface acting as part of the aspects of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of sex, the result shows both Male and Female employees of a government hospital obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 3.86 and 3.85 with standard deviation of 0.991 and 1.095 respectively.

Deep acting as part of the aspects of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of sex, the result shows both Male and Female employees of a government hospital obtained a high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 4.43 and 4.54 with the standard deviation of 0.767 and 0.697 respectively.

Staff from mental health unit explained: "As far as she knows surface acting is about denying once emotion, if the result is high, it is not unhealthy employees will be stressed out. Male and female employees are only in the moderately high level of emotional labor because she thinks that it is more about their stress management, that no matter how busy or if they have a lot of workloads. They still managed their emotions"

Having this moderately high level of emotional labor represents that male and female employees in a government hospital are able to manage their emotions required for the job. As this result represents the same level of emotional labor as to gender aspect. In the hospital, male and female may both be engaged in the same level of emotional labor as they do have the same level of responsibility and as well as the same treatment when they are facing patients/clients.

In emotional labor contexts, positive emotional requirements are more congruent with social norms for women than men (Hochschild 1983), but evidence for gender differences in emotional labor frequency are mixed (Grandey & Gabriel, 2015). The study by Basim et al. (2013), however, concluded that gender and age had a negative impact on surface acting, yet it had a positive impact on naturally-felt emotions.

In the demographic variable of age, the result shows that employees in the age range of 18-25 y/o, 26-41 y/o, 42-65 y/o of a government hospital, obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor. In the breakdown of result, employees with the age range of 18-25 y/o obtained a higher result compared to age group of 26-41 with a mean score of 4.15 and age group of 42-65 y/o with a mean score of 4.07 with the standard deviation of 0.491, 0.756 and 0.777 respectively.

Surface acting as part of the aspect of emotional labor. In the demographic variable of age, the result shows that employees in the age range of 18-25 y/o, 26-41 y/o, 42-65 y/o of a government hospital, obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 4.23, 3.89 and 3.67 with standard deviation of 0.669, 1.043 and 1.118 respectively.

Deep acting as part of the aspect of emotional labor. In the demographic variable of age, the result shows that employees in the age range of 18-25 y/o of a government hospital, obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 4.25 with standard deviation of 0.695, while in the age range of 26-41 y/o and 42-65 y/o obtained a high level of emotional labor having a mean score of 4.48 and 4.58 with standard deviation of 0.744 and 0.690 respectively.

An administrative staff said: "In my opinion, when you get older, you know how manage your emotions well. Well, of course it is because of your experiences may be, but I think as you walk in this world each day you'll be able to get learnings as how you will manage stress the burn out that might affect your day to day encounter with patients or clients"

The result as to the variable of age in the level of emotional labor, it is also in moderately high, same management of feelings as to the age groups. The result only defers to deep acting, that younger age group 18-25 obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, while age group of 26-41 and 42-65 years old obtained a high level of deep acting which is a good result that means older age group are able to manage their emotions on a high level. The reason is that, older staff are more experienced and used into management of their emotions or feelings. Older staff tend to be good in stress management for the have handles for example more patients considering their age, and they already know the strategies on how to deal with mad patience.

People get good at management of emotions as they get older. Since they authenticize themselves better with display rules, their acts become more genuine and effortful. (İríguler & Guler, 2016). This reflects the result in the deep acting which ages 26-41 years old 42-65 years old got a high level of emotional labor while ages 18-25 years old obtained a moderately high emotional labor. Within all age groups, people with 16-20 (younger group) years' experience choose to display genuine acting more than other age groups in the course of their interactions (İríguler & Guler, 2016). Gender and age had a negative impact on surface acting, yet it had a positive impact on naturally-felt emotions. Nonetheless, neither study reported in whose favor these impacts have been (Basim et al., 2013).

In the demographic variable of length of service, the result shows that employees in the tenure of service of 5 years and below, 6-10 years, 11-15 years and 16 years and above of a government hospital obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor with the standard deviation of 0.765, 0.714, 0.869 and 0.731 respectively. Employees with the tenure of service for 16 years and above, obtained a highest mean score of 4.19, 6-10 years with 4.18 mean score, 5 years and below with mean score of 4.08 and employees in the service for 11-15 years obtained the lowest mean score of 4.03.

Surface acting as part of the aspect of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of length of service, the result shows that employees in the tenure of service of 5 years and below, 6-10 years, 11-15 years and 16 years and above of a government hospital obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor having the mean score of 3.83, 3.93 and 3.62 and 3.78 with standard deviation result of 1.022, 1.011, 1.371 and 1.052 respectively.

Deep acting as part of the aspect of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of length of service, the result shows that employees in the tenure of service of 5 years and below, 6-10 years, 11-15 years and 16 years and above of a government hospital obtained a high level of emotional labor having the mean score of 4.39, 4.50, 4.57 and 4.71 with standard deviation result of 0.749, 0.738, 0.593 and 0.682 respectively.

A medical doctor said: "Those who are in service for 8 years and above are good in managing mental and emotional concerns. This is for the reason that with their tenure in the organization, they know how to deal with patients even how angry or bitter they are. He thinks that, tenured employees are good in faking their emotions if they are stressed."

In contrary to the result, that all length of service groups, the result shows that all obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor. In the institution, one staff believed that tenured staffs are more likely know how to manage stress than the new ones. But in the study, the result implies the same level of emotional labor whether new or tenured to the service. Tenured staff in the institution gained a lot of experience in terms of managing their emotions. During patient encounter, those who served longer in the institution are able to know how to handle well the concerns of the patients.

In all these cases, HCW with a shorter length of service score higher in all the stressors of EL than those who have a greater length of service (Augusto Landa et al., 2008). Non-actors had higher tenure than low actors, and regulators and deep actors had higher levels of job tenure than non-actors (Gabriel et al., 2015).

The demographic variable of status of employment, the result shows both Plantilla and Job Order employees of a government hospital obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 4.09 and 4.31 with the standard deviation of 0.743 and 0.738 respectively.

Surface acting as part of the aspect of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of status of employment, the result shows both Plantilla and Job Order employees of a government hospital obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 3.82 and 3.99 with standard deviation of 1.041 and 1.080 respectively.

Deep acting as part of the aspect of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of status of employment, the result shows both Plantilla and Job Order employees of a government hospital obtained a high level of emotional labor, having the mean score of 4.43 and 4.73 with standard deviation of 0.722 and 0.717 respectively.

Opinion from one staff of the hospital: "For both plantilla and JO in our case, the level of emotional labor do not vary because it we are the same human we feel the same. I don't think that status of employment is a significant factor in the determinants of level of emotional labor"

The result for both plantilla and job order personnel is just the same in terms of the level of emotional labor as to the different aspects of surface and deep acting. This implies that the effective management of emotion do not vary based on the employment status. On the other side, it is believed also that job order staff are careful when showing their emotions or managing their emotions it is for the reason that, they need to perform well so that they may achieve regularization and will have a high performance evaluation. Job order staff shows more accommodating mood to show the organization how effective they are in dealing with clients.

Division Assigned. In the demographic variable of division assigned, the result shows that employees of a government hospital in the HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC division and Medical/Allied Medical Division and Nursing Division obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor having the mean score of 4.12, 4.12 and 4.18 with the standard deviation result of 0.821, 0.742 and 0.697 respectively.

Surface acting as part of the aspect of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of division assigned, the result shows that employees of a government hospital in the HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC division and Medical/Allied Medical Division and Nursing Division obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor having the mean score of 3.80, 3.75 and 4.11 with standard deviation of 1.158, 1.037 and 0.948 respectively.

Deep acting as part of the aspect of Emotional Labor. In the demographic variable of division assigned, the result shows that employees of a government hospital in the HOPSSD/Finance/Offices under MCC division and Medical/Allied Medical Division obtained a high level of emotional labor having the mean score of 4.52 and 4.58 with standard deviation of 0.630 and 0.659 respectively, while the Nursing Division obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor having the mean score of 4.26 with standard deviation of 0.893.

From an informal short interview from the nursing division staff "In the part of deep acting, she don't know if she is right, it is putting too much effort to feel what the required emotion is. For her, it is only moderately high as to deep acting, because she thinks that it is because of the number of patients they handle, they are getting used to not putting too much effort in displaying required emotion."

Deep acting is a positive manifestation of good mental health because you are trying to be genuine with what you are feeling while surface acting that it is more of faking emotions. The result turned out to be high on HOPSSD/Finance/Office under MCC and Medical/Allied Medical Division and moderately high to nursing division, this implies also a good management of emotion as to the different divisions of the hospital. It is noted that it is only moderately high as to the deep acting for the nursing division because of the number of cases or patients that they are handling that they may get tired that it will be difficult for them to manage their emotions sometimes.

Table 3

Difference in the Extent of Organizational Support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according variables used in the study.

Variable	p	Significance @ 0.05	Decision
Sex	0.823	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Status of Employment	0.259	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Age	0.072	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Length of Service	0.454	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Division Assigned	0.000	Significant	Reject Ho

Mann Whitney U test was used to determine the significant difference in the organizational support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according to sex, and status of employment, while Kruskal Wallis when grouped according to age, length of service, division assigned. Status of employment. There was no significant difference in the organizational support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according to sex $p=0.823$, status of employment $p=0.259$, age $p=0.072$, and length of service $p=0.454$. There was significant difference in the organizational support for the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according to division assigned $p=0.000$. Post hoc test using Duncan's revealed that respondents from nursing division had significantly lower organizational support than other departments.

Demographic variable sex shows no significant difference in the extent of organizational support when grouped according sex. The result reveals that the p-value of .0823 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p>0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

One hospital personnel shared that: *"Based on the data shown, sex for her is not a big factor in terms of the extent of organizational support. Both male and female employees feel the same extent of support from the organization, as well as organization provide equal opportunity and same level of support"*

The data implies that there was no significant difference in the extent of organizational support in terms of sex. Even considering gender differences, same extent of organizational support were felt by both Male and Female employees. Indeed, if organizations are less supportive, our findings suggest that their male employees would cut back on their organizational support (and women, too, albeit to a lesser extent). Furthermore, POS is linked with several other positive outcomes (Kurtessis et al., 2017). Therefore, we recommend instead that organizations find ways to ensure that women are being recognized and appropriately rewarded for their contributions to the organization (Thompson et al., 2020).

Length of Service as a demographic variable shows no significant difference in the extent of organizational support when grouped according to length of service. The result reveals that the p-value of .0454 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p>0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

One of the respondents said: *"Older employees must be encouraged and rewarded more, especially those who are in like 20 years in above of service; they have shown loyalty and commitment. They must be more appreciated and supported"*

The data implies that there was no significant difference in the extent of organizational support in terms of length of service. Same extent of organizational support was felt by employees regardless of their years in service. However, basing on the stakeholders perspective, tenured employees should be given more encouragement and be rewarded because the management needs to recognize more their effort and they need to be appreciated because of the things they have done for the organization.

For instance, employee recognition programs, pay-for-performance schemes, promotions, autonomy and training may be perceived as initiatives that the employer values employees and cares about their wellbeing. This finding suggests that employers should re-think encouraging older employees with a relatively long employment record with the organization to take early retirement (Shantz et al., 2013). Tenure and perceived organizational support were found to have a similar relationship.

Division assigned as a variable shows significant difference in the extent of organizational support when grouped according to division assigned. The result reveals that the p-value of .0000 is lower than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p>0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

One of the Health Emergency Management Bureau said: *"During this pandemic, their resiliency as nurses is being tested. They need moral, emotional and financial support. Especially on their mental and emotional side, this is the reason why they are very particular about being appreciated and supported by the organization"*

The data implies that there is a significant difference in the extent of organizational support in terms of division assigned. Same extent of organizational support was felt by employees in the HOPSSD/Finance/Office under MCC and Medical/Allied Medical Division, on the other hand the nursing division rated only "moderately great" the extent of organizational support of the institution, the result varied significantly because nurses felt more stress during the time of pandemic and need much emotional and mental support from the organization.

The stress level might vary among nurses because the stress is an individual experience. The success or failure in dealing with new or recurrent stressors is reflected by nurse's support system and nurse's ability to adapt. Therefore, for organizations, it is important to provide organizational support for nurses to help them dealing with their recurrent stressors (Khrais et al., 2018). In the nursing circumstances, staffs needs organizational support to keep them provoked and delivers best care for patients (Zeinhom et al., 2016).

Table 4

Difference in the Level of Emotional Labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according to variables used in the study

Variable	p	Significance @ 0.05	Decision
Sex	0.540	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Status of Employment	0.089	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Age	0.734	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Length of Service	0.221	Not Significant	Accept Ho
Division Assigned	0.714	Not Significant	Accept Ho

Mann Whitney U-test was used to determine the significant difference in the level of emotional labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according to sex, and status of employment, while Kruskal Wallis when grouped according to age, length of service, division assigned, status of employment. There was no significant difference in the level of emotional labor of the Employees in a Government Hospital in Negros Occidental in the time of COVID-19 Pandemic when grouped according to sex $p=0.540$, status of employment $p=0.089$, age $p=0.734$, length of service $p=0.221$ and division assigned $p=0.714$.

Demographic variable sex shows no significant difference in the level of emotional labor when grouped according to sex. The result reveals that the p-value of .540 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p>0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

One of the respondents said: *"Male employees are showing high level of emotional labor, this for the reason that women are more patient and understanding. That is in his own observation"*

The data implies that there was no significant difference in the level of emotional labor in terms of sex. Same level of emotional labor obtained regardless of gender differences.

Both male and female tour leaders can perform emotional labor well in their own ways (Wong & Wang, 2009). Gender constitutes yet another important individual factor affecting emotional labor e.g.,. Many societies share a similar pattern of gender role expectations, which expect males to be rational, assertive, aggressive, independent, masterful, etc. (Zhang et al., 2022).

Length of Service shows no significant difference in the level of emotional labor when grouped according to length of service. The result reveals that the p-value of .0221 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p>0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

One of the hospital staff shared: "Tenured or experienced employees are likely to be expert in managing their emotions compared to neophyte. This is because of their years in service of facing a lot of patients"

The data implies that there was no significant difference in the level of emotional labor in terms of length of service. Same level of emotional labor obtained regardless of their years in service. As to the stakeholders opinion, because of a lot of patients that the tenured employees catered, they are more like to be better in managing their own emotions as what should be the right emotions required for the job.

Wong & Wang (2009) claimed that employees with less experience or occupational tenure are likely to experience more emotional labor.

As to the Division assigned there was no significant difference in the extent of organizational support when grouped according to length of service. The result reveals that the p-value of .0714 is greater than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is accepted.

One department head shared: *All the offices, department, or division of the hospital do have the same level of emotional labor. In this time of pandemic, even how tired and stressed you are, you need to maintain your composure because patients and clients are experiencing bad days too.*

The data implies that there was no significant difference in the level of emotional labor in terms of division assigned. Same level of emotional labor obtained regardless of their division. Regardless of the division, although they have different functions, duties and responsibilities, they show the same level of emotional labor in facing their patients or clients.

Table 5

Relationship Between Organizational Support and Emotional Labor

Correlates	r	p	Significance @ 0.05	decision
Overall Organizational Support Emotional Labor	0.190	0.001	Significant	Reject

In other words, it is not assumed that emotional labor will have a negative impact on individual well-being as a whole, but it is suggested that an approach according to its subtype is needed. Korea's medical services are overcrowded, and nurses in Korea are required to take on high levels of emotional labor and work intensely (Ha et al., 2021). Table 5 shows significant relationship between organizational support and emotional labor. The result reveals that the p-value of .0001 is lower than the alpha level of 0.05 ($p > 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

A Medical Doctor said: *"When the hospital is giving much attention and support to employees, I think they will be more motivated and satisfied, thus, they will display a good emotion or mood to patients. Organizational support affects every level of emotional labor for healthcare workers"*

The result implies significant relationship between the variables of organizational support and emotional labor. Organizations need to focus on organizational practices as employees' perception of organizational support is related to the way they express their emotions during customer interactions (Mishra, 2014). A strong sense of organizational support will also promote a stronger professional identity; further, a strong professional identity completely mediates the effect of perceived organizational support on emotional labor (Zeng et al., 2021).

Table 6

Joint Display of the Quantitative and Qualitative Results

Quantitative Results	Qualitative Themes	Meta-inferences
Moderately high level of emotional labor	Theme 1. Challenges experienced by healthcare workers	A. Employees emotional well-being
Moderately high level of surface acting	1.1 Mental and Emotional Health Concerns	
High level of Deep Acting	1.2 Social Stigma and Discrimination	
	1.3 Workplace changes during the pandemic	
	1.4 Workplace challenges brought by the pandemic	
Great extent of Organizational Support	Theme 2. Support for frontline healthcare workers	A. Integration of Rewards and recognition
Great extent of Perceived Organizational Support	Theme 3. Pulling through COVID-19	
	Theme 4. Healthcare workers resilience.	Strengthening of Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE)
Organizational Rewards		
Organizational Empowerment		

Table 6 shows the relationship of the results of quantitative and qualitative analysis. In the variable of organizational support, it links to the themes of qualitative result of support for frontline healthcare workers, pulling through COVID-19 and healthcare workers resilience. Organizational support plays a very important role in the employees' survival of the challenges of COVID-19 and it contributes also to the resilience of healthcare workers. Healthcare workers are playing crucial roles during the COVID-19 pandemic (Adalja et al., 2020).

Yet, they also face great challenges such as the fear of being infected and infecting others, heavy workloads, and a lack of personal protection equipment (Liu et al., 2020; Shanafelt et al., 2020). Organizational support is an important factor in maintaining employees' morale and it is crucial to know the perception of employees of the organizational support that they perceived to have from the employers and managers at workplace (Islahuddin, 2020).

As to the variable of emotional labor, the theme challenges experienced by healthcare workers are connected. The following sub-themes, Mental and Emotional Health Concerns, Social Stigma and Discrimination, workplace changes during the pandemic and workplace challenges brought by the pandemic affects the emotional well-being of the employees that this may contribute to their level of emotional labor whether for surface acting or deep acting. In addition to the existing challenges associated with practicing emotional labor in healthcare, the spread of the COVID-19 virus presents some major hurdles for healthcare personnel. From patient care and prolonged working hours to the high probability of infection of self or a family member, COVID-19 has considerably taken a toll on healthcare workers' mental well-being. Furthermore, an increasing number of cases has overwhelmed the healthcare systems worldwide (Javed & Batool, 2021). To help alleviate the anxiety of the healthcare workers, healthcare organizations ought to provide specific support to address their workers' concerns during the pandemic (Zhang et al., 2020).

Conclusion:

The findings provide clear insights that employees of a government hospital are satisfied with extent of organizational support that the organization is providing them. Based on the aspects of organizational support that includes; perceived organizational support, organizational empowerment and organizational rewards, employees rated these aspects as to great or to great extent of organizational support. However, it noted that in on the part of the demographic variable in the division assigned, the employees under the nursing division rated the extent of organizational support as moderately great following the same rating as to the different aspects of organizational support.

On the part of Level of Emotional Labor, the overall result obtained a moderately high level of emotional labor. Furthermore, it is also noted that on the aspect of deep acting, the result showed a high level of emotional labor for the employees of a government hospital.

Lastly, there is a significant relationship between organizational support and emotional labor. If the employees feel organizational support, it affects their emotional well-being, thus, displaying a better mood or emotions

during their tour of duty in dealing with clients or patients.. If the employees feel organization's support, it affects their emotional well-being, thus, displaying a better mood or emotions during their tour of duty in dealing with clients or patients.

Based on the result of the study, there is a specific area for improvement the researcher would recommend to the management: 1) Improvement of the wellness program for the employees, especially those undergoing COVID Rotation; 2) Strengthening the Program on Awards and Incentives for Service Excellence (PRAISE); and 3) further study related on this topic shall be conducted.

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